

THE GENERAL STATE OF AGRICULTURE IN THE FERGHANA REGION IN THE YEARS AFTER THE WAR (1946-1953)

Yusupov Jurabek Hasanboevich

basic doctoral student of Fergana State University

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада 1946-1953 йиллар даврий чегарасида Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалигининг умумий аҳволи масаласи Фарғона вилояти мисолида ўрганилган. Фарғона вилояти қишлоқ хўжалигида янги ерларнинг ўзлаштирилиши, янги очилган ерларда пахтачиликнинг кенг йўлга қўйилиши, пахта яккаҳоқимлигининг вилоят қишлоқ хўжалиги ва аҳоли турмуш тарзига таъсири масаласи таҳлил этилган.

Калит сўзлар: Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги, Фарғона вилояти, Марказий Фарғона чўли, пахтачилик, пахта яккаҳоқимлиги, ирригация қурилиши, деҳқончилик, ипакчилик, маиший ҳаёт.

Аннотация. В данной статье на примере Ферганской области исследован вопрос общего состояния сельского хозяйства Узбекистана в период 1946-1953 годов. Проанализированы вопросы освоения новых земель в сельском хозяйстве Ферганской области, широкого внедрения хлопководства на вновь освоенных землях, влияния монокультуры хлопка на сельское хозяйство и образ жизни населения области.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство Узбекистана, Ферганская область, Центрально-Ферганская пустыня, хлопководство, хлопковая монокультура, ирригационное строительство, земледелие, шелководство, бытовая жизнь.

Annotation. In this article, the question of the general state of agriculture in Uzbekistan in 1946-1953 was studied on the example of the Ferghana region. The issues of developing new lands in the agriculture of the Ferghana region, the widespread introduction of cotton cultivation on newly developed lands, the influence of cotton monoculture on the agriculture and lifestyle of the region's population were analyzed.

Keywords: agriculture of Uzbekistan, Fergana region, Central Fergana desert, cotton growing, cotton monoculture, irrigation construction, agriculture, sericulture, household life.

During the Second World War, the economy of Uzbekistan suffered greatly; food products, clothing, equipment, cars and tractors produced in the republic were used only for the front. The situation in agriculture was especially difficult. Men, the main workforce who had to work in the fields, had just returned from the

front. Most of them returned disabled, and those who returned to their villages healthy had forgotten a lot because of the war, and their work skills had greatly declined.

During the war, the material and production base of collective and state farms was completely destroyed. As a result of military losses, the number of agricultural labor force was significantly reduced. At the beginning of 1946, the working population of collective farms had decreased by 1/3 compared to 1940, and workers constituted only 40% of the pre-war level [1. B.123]. For this reason, the post-war restoration of agriculture began to take place in such difficult conditions.

The Soviet people were faced with the task of restoring and improving such a difficult economy. In August 1945, the government of the USSR developed the 4th Five-Year Plan for the Development of the National Economy for 1946-1950. According to it, the country's national income was to increase by 38 percent, but if we take into account the country's material losses during the war, this meant reaching the pre-war level [2. B.7].

In the post-war years, the main criterion for the restoration of the republic's agriculture remained the consistent expansion of cotton-sown areas and an increase in the share of cotton in the total sown areas. In addition, in the five-year plan for 1946-1950, Uzbekistan was given the main place as the main guarantee of the independence of the Cotton Union. Soon after the end of the war, in February 1946, the central political leadership adopted a special decision defining plans and measures for the restoration and further development of cotton growing in Uzbekistan in 1946-1953. Local authorities were instructed to take measures to reduce the sowing of grain crops on irrigated lands and move these crops to other lands, freeing up 218 thousand hectares of irrigated land for seeds and alfalfa [3. B.506].

On June 14, 1945, the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) and the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR issued a resolution "On measures to restore and further develop cotton production in Uzbekistan" [4. B.862-866]. According to this decision, the total area of cotton crops in the republic in 1940 was 920 thousand hectares, and by the end of 1950 it should be increased to 955 thousand hectares. In 1947, it was planned to completely restore the pre-war level of cotton production. Rural workers of Uzbekistan had to increase the cotton yield annually by developing new lands. According to the five-year plan, by 1950, the cotton harvest in the republic should reach 2 million 139 thousand tons. This figure should be 2.5 times more

than in 1945. It was also planned to increase the yield of 1 million hectares of cotton fields to 25 c/ha by 1953 [5. B.465].

Serious attention was paid to the development of other branches of agriculture, especially cattle breeding. The rapid development of new lands for sowing alfalfa and other forage crops made it possible to create a solid forage base for increasing the hooves of livestock. In the five-year plan, much attention was paid to cocooning - one of the main branches of agriculture in the republic. In 1946-1950, the task was set to breed new varieties of mulberry and new varieties of worm seeds, improve the care of silkworms and improve the quality of worm seeds. By the end of the five-year plan, it was decided to increase the amount of worm seeds distributed for sericulture to 285 thousand boxes, and the gross output of cocoons to 14,840 tons, and also to increase the output of cocoons obtained from feeding each box of silkworms. worm seeds up to 52 kilograms [6. B.135].

The five-year plan defined specific tasks and main directions for the development of each region of Uzbekistan. For example, the Fergana Valley should be developed as the main center for the production of cotton, cocoons and gas, as well as an oil-producing region. It was also planned to restore and expand the area of gardens and vineyards in the Fergana region, improve their maintenance, increase the yield of gardens and vineyards and field crops [7. B.23-24].

In the post-war years, Uzbekistan had uncultivated wastelands. According to the government decision in 1947, in the Tashkent region 46.9 thousand hectares, in Fergana 20.3 thousand hectares, in Namangan 15.3 thousand hectares, in Andijan 33 thousand hectares, in Samarkand 21.7 thousand hectares, in Bukhara 23.2 thousand hectares, in Kashkadarya 21 thousand hectares, 10.4 thousand hectares in the Surkhandarya region, 30 thousand hectares in Khorezm and Karakalpakstan. It was necessary to ensure the sowing of agricultural crops on 38.9 thousand hectares of fallow and neglected lands [8. B.178].

In the first post-war years, large-scale programs were adopted to train highly qualified specialists and provide agricultural enterprises with specialists. Particular attention was paid to increasing the number of machine operators, technical personnel and skilled workers in various branches of agriculture. However, the personnel was mainly staffed by women and teenagers who did not have the necessary professional skills. It should be noted that in the first post-war years, there were serious problems in the practice of teaching the profession of a machine operator. In particular, there were too few qualified

teachers, the necessary teaching aids and equipment were missing, and those that existed were insufficient. In 1946, agricultural production in the USSR barely reached half of the pre-war level. As a result of maintaining the rationing system for food distribution in the country, the majority of the population will be forced to work in a semi-starved state. The situation was aggravated by the drought and crop failure of 1946-1947. However, despite this, 10% of the grain harvested in the country was exported to Eastern European countries [9. B.38]. Since 1946, the amount of grain and other food and industrial goods imported to Uzbekistan from the Center depended on the amount of imported cotton. In 1946, the republic received a high cotton harvest. The state received 1 million 428 thousand tons of raw cotton, the state plan was fulfilled by 100.7%, the yield was 13.6 c/ha [10. B.222]. By 1947, the area under cotton reached the pre-war level. In 1947, 1948 and 1949, the state plan for cotton cultivation was not fulfilled. The main reason for this was the shortage of labor in agriculture, as well as the very low material and technical base of cotton growing. Thanks to the measures taken and practical assistance, in 1950, 2 million 282 thousand tons of cotton were grown in Uzbekistan, and the state plan was fulfilled by 104%. The post-war state plan for cotton cultivation for 1946-1955 was implemented only in 1946 and 1950. In 1951-1955, Uzbekistan supplied the country with 12 million 714 thousand tons of cotton. This figure was 4 million 779 thousand tons, or 62.2% more than in 1946-1951 [11. B.41]. The increase in cotton cultivation occurred mainly due to the conversion of new additional lands into cotton fields. On April 16, 1949, the government of the republic adopted a resolution "On further measures for the development of Mirzachol," and the bulk of the newly developed lands in this area were allocated for sowing cotton [12. B.286]. Although increased attention was paid to the development of water management in those years, it was directed only at irrigating collective farm lands.

Water was used mainly for cotton fields, while grain, vegetables, rice, gardens and other crops remained secondary. Due to the lack of water, household plots of villagers in many regions were not irrigated. The imperial policy based on the monopolization of cotton and economic coercion had a serious negative impact on the state of agriculture. For example, in the early 1950s, the total sown area had not yet reached the pre-war level. In the early 1950s, the gross harvest of grain crops decreased from 615.1 thousand tons in 1940 to 443 thousand tons, vegetables - from 1315.2 thousand tons to 840.2 thousand tons, sugar cane yield - from 331.9 thousand tons to 153.4 thousand tons. At the same time, the yield

of vegetable crops decreased from 125 to 73 centners per hectare, and rice from 84 to 66 centners [13. B.111].

In the context of economic difficulties, the state increased repressive measures against citizens. The decrees of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR of June 4, 1947, "On criminal liability for theft of state and public property" and "On strengthening the protection of private property of citizens" exceeded the law of August 7, 1932 (the "Law of the Five Thorns") in their cruelty. In the second half of 1946, two decisions were made to strengthen grain protection: June 27 - "On measures to ensure grain protection, prevent embezzlement, robbery and theft" and October 25 "On ensuring the safety of state grain". The decrees provided for extremely harsh measures - the replacement of the death penalty or the death penalty with 10 years of imprisonment [14. B.12]. In the spring of 1947, the cessation of grain supplies to the domestic market and a sharp increase in grain prices led to an outbreak of food theft in the country. Punishments for petty theft were sharply tightened, with 7-10 years of imprisonment introduced. However, previously such a crime was punishable by 1 year of imprisonment. People stole in order to survive. Because many collective farmers did not receive a single gram of grain for their workdays [15. B.94].

It was possible to prevent the famine that occurred in the Soviet state, to save the population from hunger and deprivation. For this, the state had sufficient reserves of grain, oil, sugar and other products. However, the existing reserves were not touched. The famine in the Soviet country in 1946 was caused not only by a natural disaster - drought, but also by the cruel and inhumane policies of the party and the Soviet government. Aid to the starving was insufficient, and if it was provided, it was symbolic.

Reducing existing food reserves or grain exports could have prevented the famine. But this was not done. In 1946, grain exports to the Soviet country amounted to 0.4 million tons, and in 1947, when thousands of people were dying of hunger, grain exports increased 6 times to 6.4 million tons [14. B.13]. The famine in the Soviet country ended only at the end of 1947.

Large capital was needed to develop agriculture. However, they did not devote themselves sufficiently to agriculture. In the post-war period, only 7 percent of all funds were directed to the needs of agricultural production in Uzbekistan. State "aid" to collective farms consisted mainly of deliveries of equipment at the disposal of MTS. At the same time, purchase prices for collective farm products remained the same as before the war, and prices for industrial products

supplied to peasant farms increased 20 times. As a result, the state received agricultural products practically for free [3. B.533-534]. In the post-war years, collective farms had to import 40-60 kg of meat, 120-280 liters of milk, and 30-150 eggs per year, depending on the soil and climate zone. Only since 1953 were the annual norms of mandatory delivery to the state somewhat reduced, and since 1958 the food obligation paid to the state was completely abolished [16. B.6].

The shortage of labor resources also affected gross agricultural production. According to statistics, in 1951 the grain harvest in the country as a whole was 82% of the 1940 figure, sunflower 65%, potatoes 77%, and vegetable crops 69% [17. B.158]. In this situation, the Soviet government took such measures as increasing taxes on agricultural activity, reducing subsidies provided to it, and abolishing benefits in order to replenish financial resources. For example, in 1952, agricultural taxes increased by 1.5–2 times compared to the previous year, and the benefits established for teachers, doctors, and agricultural specialists in land use were completely abolished [17. B.156].

Such unconventional measures did not lead to a sharp increase in agricultural production, but, on the contrary, worsened the difficult situation in the industry. The need for fundamental reforms in agriculture became more obvious. Reorganizational measures in this area required changes in a number of systems adopted in previous years as a result of the collectivization of agriculture. In the process of collectivization of agriculture, a centralized management system was created in order to establish production in the village with the help of technology, as well as to increase the efficiency of the agricultural sector. As a result, small production and private subsidiary farms within collective farms were sharply reduced.

The measures taken by the Soviet government to restore agriculture in the post-war years were based mainly on the consolidation of small collective farms, the consolidation of farms, or the transformation of collective farms into state farms (sovkhozes). If in 1940 there were 235.5 thousand collective farms in the USSR, then by 1950 they had decreased to 121.4 thousand, in 1960 - to 44 thousand, and in 1971 - to 32.3 thousand [18. B.475]. In practice, rich and prosperous collective farms were merged with poor, helpless collective farms. The goal of consolidating collective farms was aimed primarily at improving the financial situation of rural producers, expanding arable land, strengthening the material and technical base of farms, and increasing the number of livestock in collective ownership [19. B.152]. By August 1950, instead of the previous 1,770 small

collective farms, 752 large collective farms were created in the Uzbek SSR. Before the unification of collective farms, each collective farm had an average of 104 farms, and after the unification, each collective farm had 231 farms. The average land area of each collective farm increased from 362 hectares to 980 hectares. As a result of the unification of collective farms, 6,582 people were laid off from the administrative and managerial staff, which made it possible to save 590,000 working days per month, including 108,000 working days in the Fergana region [20. B.187]. The consolidation of small collective farms led to the creation of large multinational farms in Uzbekistan. This result, on the one hand, was aimed at implementing the Soviet national policy of mutual integration of a multi-ethnic and diverse cultural society (representatives of the migrant population and the local population), and on the other hand, specialization was achieved in production activities among various ethnic groups.

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